

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN IMMUNITY AND AGING IN *D. MELANOGASTER*

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Abstract

Human populations have variations in lifespan, aging, and immunity and generally experience worsened immune defense at old ages. Understanding the relationship between aging and immune defense is facilitated through model organism research, including the fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster*. In *D.melanogaster*, some aspects of immunity improve with age, but others get worse. For instance, studies depict that the process of undergoing selection for improved immunity directly favors the activation of canonical immune defense genes, which directly target pathogens but can sometimes have detrimental effects on lifespan. These genes are classified as antagonistic. Meanwhile, in studies that depict a selection for improved longevity in pathogen-free environments, the evolved longevity is associated with enhanced overall robustness and stress resistance and improvements in immune function without directly targeting classical immune-specific genes. These genes are classified as cooperative and improve the host condition broadly, allowing the host to better tolerate pathogenic infection.

Introduction:

The immune system plays a pivotal role in the ability to undergo maintenance of overall health and the ability to defend against pathogen presence. In mammals, there are two distinct parts of the immune system, innate and adaptive, which enable mammals to precisely detect and fight off infection while also obtaining recognition of their own host's cells (to protect from its attacking) and obtaining memory of the pathogen itself for future utilization against similar pathogens. However, it is also vital to limit immune responses after pathogen destruction. The ability to limit a response of the immune system is of importance as the deficiency in limiting responses can enable the creation of inflammation and autoimmune diseases.

The innate immunity is the first line of defense within all living organisms and is primarily in charge of detecting and fighting off infections through the different components of the host: anatomic, physiological (e.g., temperature denatures and overall deters microbes), phagocytic cells (engulf foreign particles), inflammation responses (enables deployment of immune resources onto injury), and antimicrobial peptides (cells that directly kill pathogens) (Marshall et al., 2018). These components are crucial within the first line of defense as they create an immediate response to threats. The adaptive immune system (which is not present in

Drosophila melanogaster immunity), is more complex and requires the utilization of other components of the cells in order to formulate memory of the pathogen exposure and provide a faster action for future immune responses.

Immune defenses are largely genetically determined, and vast amounts of genetic diversity are maintained for genes that influence immune defense. Genes related to immunity are sometimes classified based on their capacity to influence either disease resistance or disease tolerance. Disease resistance genes are thought to cause the clearance of pathogens or reducing the effectiveness of the pathogens by the immune system's physiological mechanisms (Ayres and Schneider, 2012; Ridha, 2023). These disease-resistance genes are also understood to indirectly cause adverse effects on the host health when continuously employing them. The disease tolerance genes, however, are more challenging to identify as they may influence a full spectrum of mechanisms that vary among species, sex, and individuals. We can visualize the complexity of employing these genes via asymptomatic infections. The mechanisms of disease tolerance may not directly target the microbe invader and instead limit the costs of infection (Martins et al., 2019; Ayres and Schneider, 2012). A prevalent case of Typhoid Mary enables the immediate visualization of disease tolerance at play through which a cook named Mary acquired pathogen *Salmonella typhi* which, by her denial of having this infection, enabled the many individuals to develop the fever and show significant ill-related symptoms to even death in some cases (Medzhitov et al., 2012; Marineli et al., 2013). The study of Belluz et al., 2015, demonstrated an experimental case of Typhoid fever in mice. This phenomenon of disease tolerance was undergone within the lab by exposing the mice to the *S. Typhimurium* strains orally, through which the researchers could distinguish that the toxigenic strain placed within the mice promoted

asymptomatic colonization and host survival. Therefore, such findings help shape the complex interaction between infection and disease tolerance.

These findings of disease tolerance mechanisms and study of the interrelationship between immunity and aging utilize model organisms. Using insect model organisms enables scientists to leverage their fast generation times, low-cost maintenance, and ease of handling in the laboratory. In such a manner, *Drosophila melanogaster* (commonly referred to as fruit fly) is observed as an ideal candidate for studying innate immunity. The *D. melanogaster* innate immune system displays similar pathways and responses to mammalian innate immunity.

In addition to the study of immunity, *D. melanogaster* is heavily utilized within evolution studies through which evolutionary biologists have been able to validate the evolutionary theories of aging experimentally. These evolutionary theories of aging are directly subject to the idea that aging is a direct causation of natural selection diminishing after the age of first reproduction in sexually reproducing populations (Rose 1991). Consequently, as stated within the piece by Rose et al., 2012, aging should be defined as the detuning of adaptation as it is directly correlated to declining natural selection forces. Although natural selection can be expressed all throughout development, the force of natural selection begins to diminish as reproduction activity begins in organisms.

Therefore, although the common notion of aging is directly correlated to a decline in physiological function, it is not always the best definition to interpret aging. Instead aging is a phase of reduction in natural selection pressures and adaptations. Therefore this theory enables us to become aware of not only the complexities of aging itself, but rather to acquire the notion of its implications onto immunity which often share substantial variation within populations.

Methods:

Within the progression of obtaining the focus point of my piece, I decided to make my position within this Honors Program proposal directly correlate to my involvement within Dr. Shahrestani's EAGR lab at California State University, Fullerton. This lab incorporates strong participation in looking at the complexity of the evolution of aging within *Drosophila melanogaster* longevity-evolved populations by examining the interactions among aging, immunity, and microbiota. In this lab I have been involved in creating long-lived fly populations from short-lived ancestors, following the protocols of Rose 1984. Populations selected for delayed age of first reproduction evolve increased lifespan as well as other trait divergence from their short-lived controls. My involvement in the lab then enabled me to converse with the laboratory director, Dr. Parvin Shahrestani, to examine the interrelationship between immunity and longevity within these fly populations and note the discrepancies occurring within previous literature articles that study these two traits.

After formulating a plan with my advisor, I began first by looking into articles that describe evolutionary theories of aging to better understand the complexity of this trait before delving into its relationship with immunity. I created an Excel file in which I listed all of the articles with keyword selections such as "aging," "experimental aging," "evolution," and "longevity." I then began reading literature that highlights immunity and underwent the same process of incorporating the articles with their different keywords onto the same Excel sheet. However, this time, I was also looking into keywords like "innate immunity," "disease resistance," and "disease tolerance." After compiling and exploring the literature necessary to address both topics independently, I underwent a literature search that examined both topics simultaneously with the keywords "immune aging," "cooperative genes," "evolved genes," and "inflammaging." All in all, I examined 60 articles that elucidated the topic and narrowed in on the articles that shaped

my thesis (Figure 1).

Figure 1 For this literature review I read 60 articles and categorized the articles by their relevance to capture specific topics that would aid me in understanding the interrelationship of immunity and longevity within *D. melanogaster* populations. The figure utilizes blue boxes to depict specific topics established within the articles (Note: some articles span multiple topics). However, the yellow boxes represent the particular number of articles that establish either human (mammalian topics) or *D. melanogaster* populations. This specific categorization of the organism demographic entails the whole scope of articles initially read.

In addition to the literature search, I underwent an analysis of the unpublished work of Dr. Shahrestani's lab, which enabled me to obtain crucial material necessary to visualize the interrelationship of the two traits studied in experimentally evolved flies that are currently found

within the campus of California State University Fullerton. These expressions are visualized within A-type, C-type, B-type, and O-type within Table 1. Which helps elucidate the discrepancies that occur within the traits selected.

RESULTS/DISCUSSION

How does immunity affect aging in Drosophila?

Immunity plays a critical role in longevity by defending the body against pathogens that can cause diseases, some associated with aging and premature death. However, overactive or improperly regulated immune responses can contribute to chronic inflammation, which is implicated in various age-related diseases, negatively impacting lifespan. In *D.melanogaster* populations, two pathways, Imd and Toll, are directly linked to the detection of pathogens, and these are differentially activated based on the characteristics of pathogens. These pathways are centered on undergoing specific expression of immune defense molecules by the overall activation of NFκB transcription factors (Libert et al. 2006). The publication by Libert et al., 2006 demonstrated that the utilization of overexpressing PGRP-LE (peptidoglycan recognition protein, an immunity-related molecule) induced not only antimicrobial peptide levels (These immunity-related molecules are classified for their ability to disrupt membrane structures of pathogens, which are essential in *D. melanogaster* defense (Hanson and Lemaitre, 2023; Diamond et al., 2009)), but resistance to a wide range of pathogens. Apart from visualizing the consequences of overexpressing PGRP-LE, this study created an inflammatory state within the fly populations, revealing a reduction in the lifespan of flies (Libert et al., 2006). Therefore, these results define that inflammatory states caused by the overuse of innate immunity enable shorter lifespans. Following the finding of Libert et al., 2006, other studies looked into the implications

of overexpression of immunity-related genes. In the case of overexpressing Relish (known to induce an immune response by regulating AMPs), increased antimicrobial peptides and, as a consequence, shortened lifespan (Badinloo et al., 2018). The study then looked into the effects of overexpressing antimicrobial peptides, which detailed that specific AMP genes (Atta, Def, MtK, and CecA10) significantly decreased lifespan within both sexes of *D. melanogaster*. However, the only antimicrobial peptides that did not impact longevity were identified as Drs and DRo. These findings illustrated by Badinloo et al., 2015 determined that the overexpression of AMPs induced cytotoxicity and shortened the lifespan. Konatidies et al., 2017 demonstrated the same visual of AMP overexpression as they decreased lifespan while analyzing the knockdown of *Relish*, which showed increased longevity. Although the study by Hanson and Lemaitre, 2023 does not look at the effects of AMP overexpressions, it establishes that the loss of these immune molecules decreases the lifespan. However, Loch et al., 2017, demonstrated a different consequence of AMP levels, determining that antimicrobial peptides extend lifespan. By focusing primarily on the antimicrobial peptides *Drosocin* and *CecA1* they were able to observe extension of overall lifespan of the adult flies (Loch et al., 2017). This study also addresses that this lifespan extension demonstrated to cause reduced activation of immune pathways which is otherwise usually addressed to increase in its activity during aging (Loch et al., 2017). Nevertheless, this study also discussed the reports of previous studies, which reveal that overexpression of multiple AMPs by constitutive induction can adversely affect survival. Therefore, we can conclude that this understanding of AMP dysregulation has had different outcomes when studying the complexity of immunity traits' impact on longevity. These outcomes imposed on the longevity of *D. melanogaster* highlight the consequences of trade-offs within

these traits in which the overactivation of specific immune responses, which are very costly, can have deleterious consequences upon lifespan itself (Garshall and Flatt, 2018).

How does aging affect immunity?

There is an establishment that typically, as organisms age, there are substantial changes in adaptive and innate immunities, which result in a rapid decline in immune defenses (Kline and Bowdish, 2015). As a consequence, we understand that longevity can have a significant impact on the immune system. Often, immune function declines as individuals age. This phenomenon, known as immunosenescence, is characterized by reduced production of new immune cells and a decline in the ability to respond to pathogens effectively. However, specific longevity-associated genes may enhance immune surveillance and repair mechanisms, potentially mitigating some of the negative effects of aging on the immune system.

The studies employing *D. melanogaster* populations have visualized the adverse effects aging imposes on immune responses. For instance, phagocytic interactions are a highly enforced mode of action against pathogens, through which they act upon the engulfing and removal of pathogens. A study depicted that the mechanism of phagocytosis, which is carried out through hemocytes within *Drosophila*, declined with age (Mackenzie et al., 2011). The results established within this study were defined to express that older flies had fewer phagocytosis levels due to a decline of hemocytes, which would have been active to undergo phagocytosis. Therefore, they decreased the overall rate of phagocytosis across all cells (Mackenzie et al., 2011). This piece demonstrates that the immune system is affected in its ability to activate the responses properly due to age being imposed as a factor. Similarly, the publication by Horn et al., 2014 depicted the derived effect older flies have on their inability to destroy pathogens due to a decline in

phagocytic regulation. Although there were discrepancies that could have been due to the different assays when compared to the findings of Mackenzie et al., 2011, for instance, the previous study depicts that the concentration of phagocytic cells decreases with age, this study by Horn et al., 2011 depicts no changes within phagocytic cells across ages. Still, this piece reveals that phagocytic events slow in older flies, which is suggested to be correlated to an accumulation of phagosomes in older flies. Apart from the findings listed by Horn et al., 2014, this piece suggests that the visual of higher bacterial loads is not solely due to a decline in active hemocytes as proposed by Mackenzie et al., 2011. Instead, Horn et al., 2014, proposes that it is the decline in function from hemocytes to engulf pathogens that cause higher bacterial loads.

By redirecting ourselves to another effect aging imposes on immunity, there are high upregulations of immune-specific cells (e.g., AMP levels), that arise with age. For instance, Zerofsky et al., 2005 displays that older flies expressed a higher induction of antimicrobial peptides when compared to younger flies. By delving into the piece, Zerofsky et al., 2005 indicated the upregulation of antimicrobial peptides is because older flies have chronic induction of immune responses when exposed to pathogens. In addition, there was an upregulation of AMP *diptercin* in older flies before exposing them to the septic jab of bacteria (Zerofsky et al., 2005). In addition, transcriptomic data from Wang et al., 2020 reveals that among all possible immune-specific genes known, only AMPs were seen to be increased in gene expression with aging, while the other expressions of those other genes stayed the same. We continue to see this phenomenon of AMP levels rising with age among other sources, such as in Kounatidis et al., 2017), which show significant increases in AMP while no changes in activation pathway expressions were displayed. Likewise, the study expressed within Hanson and Lemaitre, 2023, establishes that the upregulation of antimicrobial peptides is a consequence of aging itself.

Therefore, these studies contextualize the overexpression of genes and the inability to respond to pathogens effectively due to aging.

What is the evolutionary relationship between immunity and aging?

Studies of the relationship between aging and immunity in *D. melanogaster* often result in mixed results in which some aspects of immunity improve with age while other aspects get worse. Laboratory experimental evolution studies enable researchers to apply an evolutionary framework to define the interrelationship between immunity and longevity. The results of Shahrestani et al., 2021 elucidate that when *D. melanogaster* populations are selected for better immunity (S type), they evolve to have shortened longevity under uninfected conditions compared to control populations (CS type) (Table 1). Specifically, after 19 generations for improved immune defense against the fungal entomopathogen *Beauveria bassiana*, compared to control populations, the selected populations had higher survival when infected with *B. bassiana* and lower survival when uninfected (Shahrestani et al. 2021). This finding implies that the traits studied, immunity and longevity, underwent an evolved trade-off. Notably, the S-type populations that became more resistant to *B. bassiana* also became resistant to another fungal pathogen, but not to gram-negative or gram-positive bacteria (Shahrestani et al. 2021) suggesting the possible involvement of genes outside of the canonical immune pathways.

Table 1 Studies that involve experimental evolution to explore the relationship between immunity and longevity. Each fly population in the studies is established differently based on their generation cycles and previous selection pressures. The first row describes two population types in Shahrestani et al., 2021. The S-type consists of flies selected specifically for improved immune defense, while the CS-type represents inbred populations used as a control. In the following two rows, Shahrestani's unpublished data details the B-type and O-type populations. The B-type has a faster generation time, while the O-type comprises experimentally evolved flies with delayed reproduction time. In the third row, there are A-types with a shorter generation time

of nine days, and C-types with a longer generation time. Continuing with Shahrestani's unpublished data, the fourth row outlines previously selected fly populations subjected to different selection pressures. The TDO line indicates fly populations selected for multiple generations against desiccation, while TSO refers to the starvation-selected populations. Despite undergoing different selection pressures, both populations followed a 21-generation cycle. Finally, the fifth row depicts populations from Nguyen et al., 2017, showing outbred flies that underwent 14 generation cycles. The S-type represents flies selected for immune defense, while the C-type serves as the control for immune defense selection.

	Longevity	immunity	
S type (selected for immune defense)	<	>	CS type (control for immune selected lines)
B-type (14-day cycles)	<	<	O-type (70 day cycle)
A-types (9-day cycles)	<	<	C-types (28 day cycle)
TDO (21 day cycles, former dessication selection)	<	=	TSO (21 day cycles, former starvation selection)
S-type (selection for immune defense)	<	>	C-type control for immune defense selected

The evolution of increased longevity reveals a correlated increase in immunity within the experimental workings of Fabian et al., 2018. In this study, the selection imposed for longevity gave different outcomes to the immunity responses. For instance, the survival post-infection against selected and control flies imposed the finding that improved survival was marked for young and aged long-lived flies (selected group) against fungus and gram-negative infection; however, against gram-positive bacteria, there was only an increased survival rate relative to the controls exhibited (Fabian et al., 2018). Additionally, bacterial clearance was also different in these populations. It was acknowledged that the control group had a higher ability to impose bacterial clearance than that of long-lived flies (Fabian et al., 2018). However, this difference

between survivorship and bacterial clearance do not contradict each other at all, seeing as the long-lived population (selected group) could have evolved to become tolerant to these pathogens indirectly. Therefore, these findings allude to the implications caused by an evolved longevity indirectly contributed to the immune responses found. This specific phenomenon is directly seen in those imposed within the EAGR lab whose longevity-evolved fly lines exhibited a higher increase in immune responses due to the same indirect implications the longevity imposed onto these evolved long-lived flies.

We continue to visualize the discrepancies between the two traits within the realm of selection, through which when evolved immune responses between selected and nonselected groups of *D. melanogaster* against *B. bassiana*. Through this, it was discovered that higher survival was expressed within selected populations infected with the entomopathogenic fungus (Nguyen et al., 2017). However, when uninfected with the fungus, the control groups obtained a higher survival rate than the selected population (Nguyen et al., 2017). Thus, selection for immune defense had decreased longevity. In such observation, the genomic analysis revealed the involvement of three immune-specific genes within this study. Therefore, perhaps the finding illustrated in both Shahrestani et al., 2021 and Nguyen et al., 2017 of an improved immunity but worsened longevity is due to the activation of immune-specific genes.

Although not listed within the established experimentally evolved studies, Carnes et al., 2015 were able to visualize the differences in longevity within B and O-type populations that were within the same family of flies from Shahrestani et al., 2021 and the unpublished Shahrestani lab material. This describes that O-type populations established a 70% increase in lifespan when compared to the B-types. However, the genomic application of this study delved

to establish divergence within the immune-specific genes between o-type and b-type populations. Therefore, both traits are different among selected populations.

Yet, there are also more discrepancies established within the relationship between immunity and longevity, which, when undergoing comparisons between populations formerly evolved for divergence in stress resistance, Phillips et al. 2018 reveal that populations that differ in longevity do not differ in immunity. This was referenced through the findings of fungal resistance assay between TDO (previously selected for desiccation resistance (ability to withstand extreme dryness); are under 3-week cycles) and TSO (previously selected for starvation resistance), which had shown that despite previous harsh selection divergence and the factor of TDO having a higher lifespan that the immunity itself did not translate to have the similar increases within this line. This finding enables the depictions of constraints longevity trait partakes to cause an effect in immunity.

The unpublished data from Shahrestani's lab correlating A-type (9-day cycles) and C-type (28-day cycles), establish an overall better immunity and longevity among the C-type populations across all ages (table 1). This was analyzed via the close examination between short-lived and long-lived populations by focusing on survival between fungus-infected and fungus-free conditions (Shahrestani's lab unpublished methods). Such an experiment revealed that death rates are expected to be higher in populations selected for accelerated development; these are the ACO populations. In addition, the long-lived populations expressed higher infection survivorship than short-lived populations and overall, the younger flies had a better immune defense than older flies (EAGR unpublished data). This revelation is congruent to what was expressed in Fabian et al., 2018. However, the genomic implications are different, which could be due to the methods themselves.

A similar implication of immunity and longevity trait interrelationship was expressed within B-type and O-type populations within the Shahrestani lab. These outbred fly populations have been maintained since 1975 and placed under the reproductive cycles of 14-day generation times. However, when undergoing experimental evolution, only the B-type flies were maintained within the same generation cycles while the O-types were delayed for reproduction and moved their generation time to 70-day cycles (Rose 1984). These fly populations were then tested for multiple traits; however, I will only highlight the traits of immunity and longevity responses. The immune defense assays were utilized to analyze the experimentally evolved O-type fly selections by examining mortality for 12 days after exposure to fungus (Shahrestani lab unpublished methods). The longevity results from this study demonstrate that O-populations evolved to enhance age-specific survival compared to B-type controls. Following such results, the immune defense assays established a higher survival post-infection among O-type flies than B-type flies. Therefore, the findings illustrate that although the infection was deemed to have lower survival, the O-type selection regime enabled improved survival. Therefore, when applying these two findings among the traits, we conclude that when selected for increased longevity, there was an increase in overall immunity. This finding follows the same discovery expressed by Fabian et al., 2018 which revealed that selection for increased longevity improved overall immune defense. This revelation enables us to acknowledge the suggestion that longevity genes enhance both traits and are classified as cooperative.

The theory of evolution provides a framework for understanding the complex interrelation between immunity and longevity. It proposes that when we delve into the inconsistencies observed between immunity and the aging process, these can be elucidated by recognizing the genetic complexity within our immune systems. This complexity involved both

antagonistic and cooperative genes. Antagonistic genes are crucial in reducing pathogen load but may indirectly inflict negative consequences on the host, such as inflammation. On the other hand, cooperative genes facilitate the host's tolerance of infections by enhancing the overall robustness, thereby potentially contributing to increased longevity. Experimental evolution studies, particularly those incorporating whole genome sequencing at various stages of the adaptive process, are invaluable for exploring this dynamic further. They enable researchers to dissect the myriad classes of genes that influence both resistance and tolerance to infections and to understand how these genetic factors interact with the processes of aging and longevity. As such, this analytical approach in the literature underscores the necessity of recognizing this novel class of cooperative genes and paves the way for the genomic identification of these elements. This field of the study suggests a shift in how we perceive the interplay between our genetic makeup and our capacity to live longer healthier lives. By adopting a more nuanced view that includes identifying and understanding cooperative genes, we stand at the threshold of unlocking new possibilities in enhancing human health and longevity. This endeavor, rooted in the principles of evolutionary theory, holds promise for providing deeper insights into the genetic foundations of immunity and aging, potentially leading to groundbreaking advancements in medical science and healthcare.

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